

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Factors that influence eating disorder tendencies in adolescents: A literature review

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Abstract

Eating disorders are any form of behavioral or habitual eating disorder that results in altered food consumption and absorption, and significantly impairs physical health and psychosocial functioning. Eating disorders are any disorder characterized primarily by pathological disturbances of food-related attitudes and behaviors, including anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, and binge-eating disorder (Sinurat, 2018). This study aims to determine the factors that influence eating disorder tendencies in adolescents. The research method utilized is literature review, which involves searching for research articles from Research Gate and Google Scholar using keywords such as eating disorder, influencing factors, anorexia nervosa, binge-eating disorder, and body image. From the research findings, it can be concluded that the occurrence of eating disorder tendencies in adolescents is caused by several dominant factors such as body image (3 articles), peer influences (3 articles), knowledge (2 articles), also family roles and BMI (2 articles).

Keywords: Eating Disorder; Influencing Factors; Anorexia Nervosa; Binge-eating Disorder; Body Image

1. Introduction

The adolescent phase is a transitional period from childhood with an orientation towards adulthood, which is characterized by growth and development in terms of psychological and physiological aspects. The World Health Organization (WHO) explains that adolescence is in the range of 10 to 19 years [1].

Eating disorders are any form of behavioral or habitual eating disorder that results in altered food consumption and absorption, and significantly impairs physical health and psychosocial functioning. Eating disorders are any disorder characterized primarily by pathological disturbances of food-related attitudes and behaviors, including anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, and binge-eating disorder [2].

The genesis of eating disorders shows a trend of increasing prevalence on women. The study conducted by Galmiche found an increase in the prevalence of global eating disorders in the 2000-2006 period by 3.5% to 7.8% for the 2013-2018 period [3]. Based on Riskesdas data, the risk of adolescents aged 15-19 years experiencing chronic energy deficiency (CED) in 2007 was 30.9% and in 2012 it rose to 46.6%. The risk of chronic energy deficiency (CHD) is caused by an imbalance in nutritional intake, so that the nutrients needed by the body are not fulfilled. The imbalance in nutrient intake can be caused by indications of eating disorders in individuals [2].

The factors that cause a person to undergo eating disorders include; individual, family, biological, and psychological. More specifically, the causes of eating disorders are lack of self-confidence, unhealthy dietary behavior and attention to excessive body image [4]. Based on the background outlined above, the aim of this research is to identify the factors influencing eating disorder tendencies in adolescents.

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2. Material and methods

This research is qualitative research that uses a literature review method with descriptive analysis. The data used in this research came from national journal scientific articles obtained from Research Gate and Google Scholar with the keywords "eating disorder", "influencing factors", "anorexia nervosa", "binge-eating disorder", and "body image". The inclusion criteria in this study were scientific articles published within the last 5 years (2018-2023). The collected data will be analyzed, and conclusions will be drawn based on the analysis.

3. Results and discussion

The following are the findings from the articles that have been collected and analyzed.

Table 1 List of Articles

No.	Author	Method	Result
1	Goutama, I. L. & Chris, A. [5]	Cross Sectional	The prevalence of factors affecting the occurrence of binge eating disorder (BED), patients with BED were found to have moderate or severe depression (40% each), moderate or severe anxiety (40% each), and mild or severe stress (40% each).
2	Oktapianingsi & Sartika, A. N. [6]	Cross Sectional	The results of bivariate analysis show that there is a significant relationship between body image and the incidence of eating disorders, with a p-value obtained of 0.019. Based on Chi-Square analysis, there is a significant relationship between adolescent girls who have a negative body image and the incidence of eating disorders, this is because not only body image can affect a person's eating disorder but there are several other factors such as knowledge and social media.
3	Kusuma, S., L., A. & Farudin, A. [7]	Cross Sectional	There is a relationship between stress levels and the risk of eating disorders in Nutrition Science students at the Faculty of Health Sciences, Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta. Most students with the risk of eating disorders are more directed towards dieting and oral control aspects.
4	Sari, T., I. & Rosyidah, R. [8]	Cross Sectional	There is an influence between body shaming on the tendency of anorexia nervosa in adolescent girls in Surabaya city. Thus body shaming has an influence on the tendency of anorexia nervosa by 13.5%, while the other 86.5% is influenced by other factors not examined by the researcher.
5	Mardiah, K. & Nurmala, I. [9]	Cross Sectional	There is a significant and unidirectional relationship between the tendency of anorexia nervosa and peers. The relationship between peers and the tendency of anorexia nervosa is positive or unidirectional, it can be interpreted that if the pressure from peers is low, then the tendency of anorexia nervosa is also low, and vice versa.
6	Adji, S. B., Fitrikasari, A., & Julianti, H., P. [10]	Cross Sectional	There is a significant relationship between body image perception and the incidence of eating disorders, namely in the appearance evaluation domain. Appearance evaluation has a significant risk of 23 times the incidence of eating disorders.
7	Lidiawati, M., Lumongga, N., & Anto. [11]	Case Control	Based on the results of bivariate analysis, there is a relationship between knowledge (0.000), attitudes (0.001), allowance (0.002), family roles (0.005), and peer roles (0.000) with eating behavior of obese adolescents.
8	Firdawiyanti, B., S., Andriani, E., & Sabrina. [12]	Cross Sectional	There is a significant relationship between intensity of social media use and body image with eating disorders. The relationship between intensity of social media use and eating disorders obtained (p-value 0.000), and the relationship between body image and eating disorders obtained (p-value 0.000).
9	Islamy, S., J., D. & Cahyanti, I., Y. [13]	Cross Sectional	There is a relationship between self-esteem and the tendency of anorexia nervosa in adolescent girls. The relationship between self-esteem and anorexia nervosa is negative or opposite, meaning that the higher the level of self-esteem, the lower

			the level of anorexia nervosa tendency. Conversely, the lower the level of self-esteem, the higher the level of anorexia nervosa tendency.
10	Rahmayanti, M., Rahmadany, J., Ayun, K., Q., Hayati, F., R., Jassey, B., & Nisa, H. [14]	Cross Sectional	The results of this study indicate that BMI is significantly associated with the tendency of deviant eating behaviour (p-value=0.000). Students with obese (BMI>25.0 kg/m ²) have a tendency to deviant eating behaviour by 2.032 times greater than students with normal BMI. This study also found that peer influence has a significant relationship with the tendency of deviant eating behaviour (p-value=0.005).

Based on the results of the review of 10 articles as presented in Table 1, this discussion will focus on identifying the dominant factors for the occurrence of eating disorder tendencies in adolescents.

The dominant factors for the occurrence of eating disorder tendencies in adolescents is body image. According to Oktapianingsi and Sartika (2022), the results showed that 53.7% of subjects had a negative body image, and 44.2% of subjects experienced eating disorders. This study concludes that there is a significant relationship between body image and eating disorders (p=0.019) with Ods Ratio = 2.221, so women with negative body image have 2 times the chance of experiencing eating disorders compared to positive body image. In line with the research of Firdawiyanti, et al. (2023) showed that the relationship between body image and eating disorders obtained (p-value=0.000) which means that there is a significant relationship between body image and eating disorders.

Another factor that has a big influence on the occurrence of eating disorder tendencies in adolescents is peer influences. According to Rahmayanti, et al. (2021) shows that there are 41.1% of respondents who have a tendency to deviant eating behavior. In addition, it is known that students who are influenced by peers regarding eating behavior have a 2.82 times greater risk of having a tendency to deviant eating behavior (95% CI: 1.37-5.82). Another study conducted by Mardiah and Nurmala (2022), the majority of respondents as many as 155 (54.2%) negatively did not get peer pressure and had a low tendency of anorexia nervosa. The relationship between peers and the tendency of anorexia nervosa is positive or unidirectional, it can be interpreted that if the pressure from peers is low, then the tendency of anorexia nervosa is also low, and vice versa.

Knowledge and family roles are also an important factors on the occurrence of eating disorder tendencies in adolescents. According to Lidiawati, et al. (2020), the knowledge of adolescents regarding obesity eating behavior is mostly categorized as good, with a number of 142 respondents (53%). The knowledge variable with an Exp (B) value of 0.821, which means that adolescents with poor knowledge tend to be 0.821 times more likely to be obese than adolescents with good knowledge. In addition, there is also influence of family roles on the eating behavior of obese adolescents (p=0.002 < p=0.05). This means that the eating behavior of obese adolescents can be influenced by parental support in providing attention about eating behavior in the family.

Another factors that influence eating disorders tendencies in adolescents is BMI. According to Rahmayanti, et al. (2021) shows that BMI is significantly associated with the tendency of deviant eating behaviour (p-value=0.000). Students with obese (BMI>25.0 kg/m²) have a tendency to deviant eating behaviour by 2.032 times greater than students with normal BMI. Adolescents who have a higher BMI tend to feel uncomfortable or ashamed of their body shape. The concept of slim and thin, which is considered as the ideal body shape, makes adolescents control their eating or reduce the amount of food they eat based on their own thoughts so that they tend to experience sedentary eating behavior.

Based on the results of the review of 10 articles as presented before, other factors that influence eating disorder tendencies in adolescents include the intensity of social media use, attitudes, allowance, stress levels, severe anxiety, severe depression, self-esteem, dieting, and body shaming can be a cause to an eating disorders.

4. Conclusion

Based on research findings, there are several factors that often appear and significantly contribute to the occurrence of eating disorder tendencies in adolescents, namely body image, peer influences, knowledge, family roles, and BMI. Based on these several factors, body image and peer influences are the dominant factor that influence eating disorder tendencies in adolescents. Apart from that, there are several other factors, namely the intensity of social media use, attitudes, allowance, stress levels, severe anxiety, severe depression, self-esteem, dieting, and body shaming that can cause eating disorders.

Compliance with ethical standards

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